

Standardised semantic enrichment of OpenBIM for machine-readable pre-demolition audits

Abstract

The transition to a circular construction sector requires reliable, machine-readable material data from existing buildings. Although reality-capture and emerging scan-to-BIM workflows increasingly support geometric modeling of existing buildings, pre-demolition audits still rely largely on manual interpretation and static reports that downstream tools cannot automatically process. The remaining obstacle is semantic. This paper presents WASTEie2IFC, a web-based framework that addresses this gap by writing audit outputs against the openly published bSDD WASTEie dictionary. The resulting IFC files carry interoperable Property Sets and European Waste Catalogue classifications rather than proprietary labels, standardizing the audit deliverable. We evaluate the framework on a historical railway station in the Czech Republic, enabling a rare ex-post validation against actual measured demolition tonnages. Residual discrepancies are traceable to upstream geometric capture limits rather than the semantic enrichment pipeline, and hazardous materials identified digitally were successfully isolated on-site. These results position the framework as a reliable foundation for digital circular-economy workflows required by emerging regulation and by secondary-material markets.

Keywords: Circular economy, Construction and demolition waste, BIM, IFC, EWC

1. Introduction

The built environment is the single largest consumer of primary raw materials and the single largest generator of solid waste in Europe (Gálvez-Martos et al., 2018; Hasselsteen et al., 2025; Khan et al., 2025). The construction sector consumes roughly 40% of the stone, gravel, and sand extracted each year, together with about a quarter of all harvested wood, and is responsible for nearly a quarter of anthropogenic air pollution (Kabirifar et al., 2020; Papamichael et al.,

2023). The downstream counterpart of this resource intensity is construction and demolition waste (CDW), which at approximately 38.4% of total waste production represents the largest material flow recorded by Eurostat (2023). Because each tonne landfilled or downcycled represents both a disposal burden and a lost opportunity to displace virgin extraction, CDW has become the priority stream through which the European Union intends to realize its transition from a linear to a circular economy (Hasibuan et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2022).

Within this transition, the pre-demolition audit is emerging as the pivotal instrument that determines whether a building leaves the stock as waste or as a source of secondary materials. The audit is a systematic assessment of the quantities, qualities, and locations of materials bound in a structure, whose purpose is to identify high-value pathways for reuse and recycling and to isolate hazardous fractions before deconstruction begins (Ehlert et al., 2019; European Commission, 2018; Zaharieva, Roumiana et al., 2024). Harmonized European guidance consolidated in the PARADE best-practice document (Wahlström et al., 2019) and in the EU CDW Management Protocol (European Commission, 2018, 2024) prescribes a workflow that combines a desk study, a site survey with physical sampling, and a structured report classifying each fraction by mass, volume, and European Waste Catalogue (EWC) code. The resulting inventory feeds material declarations, selective dismantling plans, and the safe-handling pathways that govern hazardous substances such as asbestos (Bonifazi et al., 2024; Strufe, 2005; Wahlström et al., 2019).

The regulatory weight placed on these audits has grown significantly in recent years, and the nature of the policy target has simultaneously changed. The Waste Framework Directive (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2008) and its 2018 amendment (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2018) established a 70% recovery target for non-hazardous CDW. However, this threshold has been routinely met through backfilling and low-grade downcycling, and has failed to deliver genuine circularity (Wu et al., 2019; Zero Waste Europe, 2021). European policy is therefore shifting upstream from aggregate recovery statistics toward mandatory, high-fidelity pre-demolition audits that steer materials into reuse and high-quality recycling (Caro et al., 2024; European Commission, 2024). The EU Level(s) framework reinforces this direction: its Macro-objective 2 on resource-efficient and circular material life cycles, to-

gether with the EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities, explicitly demands interoperable, verifiable, and machine-readable data on material flows (Dodd et al., 2020; Díaz-López et al., 2021; European Commission, 2024; Honic and De Wolf, 2023). Member states are translating this demand into national procedures, with Germany’s DIN SPEC 91484:2023 formalizing a two-stage audit prioritizing high-quality reutilization (Deutsches Institut für Normung, 2023), France mandating the statutory PEMD diagnosis linked to a centralized digital reporting platform (French Republic, 2020), and the Netherlands coupling audits to secondary-aggregate certification under BRL 2506 (Stichting Bouwkwaliiteit, 2021); convergence at the European level is being coordinated through CEN/TC 350/SC1 on Circular Economy in Construction (European Commission, 2024).

Against this maturing regulatory backdrop, audit practice itself has remained stubbornly analogue. Assessments still rely predominantly on site visits, visual inspection, and tape-measure geometry, producing reports that are subjective, difficult to reproduce, and largely confined to PDF or spreadsheet formats (Byers et al., 2024; Rašković et al., 2020; Spišáková et al., 2021). Such static documents cannot be queried, validated, or ingested by the automated workflows that secondary-material markets, life cycle assessment (LCA) tools, and compliance platforms increasingly require (Amarasinghe et al., 2025; Byers et al., 2024; Kuzminykh et al., 2024; Çetin et al., 2023). Closing this gap demands that the audit evolve into a structured, machine-readable dataset rather than a document, and that the underlying building geometry be captured with a fidelity that matches the expectations of downstream digital consumers.

Reality-capture technologies and building information modeling (BIM) provide the geometric substrate for such an evolution (Sacks et al., 2018). For buildings with incomplete as-built documentation, which dominate the existing stock targeted by audits, LiDAR and photogrammetry can reconstruct three-dimensional representations of arbitrary spatial complexity (Chen and Luo, 2026). Advances in deep learning and point-cloud processing have made the conversion of these captures into semantically segmented BIM models increasingly automated (Chen et al., 2019; Mahmoud et al., 2025; You et al., 2026a; Zbirovský and Nežerka, 2025), and dedicated tools such as Cloud2BIM (Nežerka and Zbirovský, 2025) have operationalized this workflow for

pre-demolition auditing. Beyond academic prototypes, commercial scan-to-BIM solutions have also begun to support this transition, indicating growing industrial demand for semi-automated modelling of existing buildings; one example is Cloud2BIM-AI, offered by the university spin-off Constriq, which applies AI-based segmentation and classification to construction elements and illustrates how research-derived scan-to-BIM methods are entering professional practice. The remaining bottleneck is therefore semantic rather than geometric: models can increasingly support reliable quantity extraction, but the material, condition, and waste-classification attributes required for a valid audit still depend on expert assessment and are commonly entered manually (Byers et al., 2024; Płoszaj-Mazurek and Tofiluk, 2026; Santos et al., 2019). Automated systems can identify a “wall” element, but they cannot yet reliably distinguish between high-value recyclable gypsum and hazardous cement-asbestos boards without physical sampling and professional liability. A human-in-the-loop approach therefore remains necessary for legal compliance and safe deconstruction planning. Emerging large language model (LLM) approaches confirm the scale of the enrichment bottleneck and the potential for digital support (Forth and De Wolf, 2026; Płoszaj-Mazurek and Tofiluk, 2026); however, their probabilistic outputs do not yet provide the deterministic reliability and verifiable certainty required for waste legislation. This study therefore excludes LLM-based enrichment and relies on auditor assessment structured through bSDD. Bridging geometry and semantics is now recognized as the decisive step for fully digital audit workflows (Kuzminykh et al., 2024; Rašković et al., 2020).

Crossing that bridge requires open, vendor-neutral data standards so that enriched models can be exchanged, validated, and reused across tools and stakeholders. The Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) standard (ISO 16739-1:2024) (Borrmann et al., 2018; buildingSMART International, 2024a), maintained by buildingSMART International, provides the schema for describing built-environment objects alongside their properties and relationships, while the buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD) (buildingSMART International, 2023a), grounded in ISO 12006-3, supplies machine-readable, software-agnostic definitions of those objects and attributes. The Information Delivery Specification (IDS) (buildingSMART International, 2023b) completes this open-BIM stack by formalizing verifiable information requirements that a model must satisfy, enabling

automated checking of whether an audit deliverable actually contains the attributes required by regulation or by a downstream stakeholder (Kuzminykh et al., 2024; Lee et al., 2026; Matoseiro Dinis et al., 2023). The strategic value of this structured data extends well beyond the demolition site: the emerging regimes of Material Passports and digital building logbooks, now anchored in the recast Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (European Parliament and Council of the European Union, 2024), depend on the same attribute-level information to feed secondary-material marketplaces, multi-criteria reuse assessments, and circular-economy decision support throughout an asset’s life (Aftab and Agliata, 2026; Alonso et al., 2023; Honic et al., 2024; Mankata et al., 2025).

To address the semantic enrichment gap specifically for CDW, the WASTEie framework (buildingSMART International, 2024b; Tetervov, 2024) was developed as an open, standardized bSDD dictionary describing the waste- and recycling-related attributes of construction materials and components. Hosted on the bSDD platform and grounded in ISO 12006-3 and ISO 23386, WASTEie extends the IFC 4.3 schema through custom property sets (Psets) that link circularity data to existing geometry without altering native definitions, thereby enabling EWC classifications to be attached directly and consistently to spatial elements via `IfcClassificationReference` and `IfcRelAssociatesClassification`. Crucially, while the auditor provides the material diagnosis, the WASTEie dictionary provides the mandatory standardized structure for that data; this prevents the common bad practice of using inconsistent nomenclature and idiosyncratic labeling that typically renders traditional reports unusable for downstream automated processing. The dictionary establishes what a machine-readable CDW audit should contain; what has so far been missing is a practical, auditor-facing pipeline that takes a raw geometric model and produces a WASTEie-compliant, EWC-classified, regulation-ready deliverable in an acceptable amount of time.

Several recent works have dealt with adjacent parts of this enrichment problem, and it is important to delineate precisely how the present contribution differs. Forth and De Wolf (2026) propose semantic property enrichment for circularity assessments using labeled property graphs: their output is a graph representation of the enriched model, which is powerful for reasoning but is

not natively interoperable with IFC-based downstream consumers without conversion. [Çetin et al. \(2023\)](#) develop a BIM-based framework for material passports of existing buildings, but rely on a project-specific SQL database and custom parameter schemes rather than a public, vendor-neutral dictionary. [Kuzminykh et al. \(2024\)](#) articulate information requirements for openBIM-based demolition digitization and prototype an implementation, but do not close the loop onto a publicly published bSDD dictionary. [Płoszaj-Mazurek and Tofiluk \(2026\)](#) explore LLM-assisted enrichment that offers scale at the cost of deterministic guarantees required for waste legislation, and earlier BIM-based pre-demolition tools, notably those produced by the HISER project, pioneered IFC-based quantity take-off but predated bSDD as an operational service and therefore relied on proprietary parameter definitions.

What distinguishes the present work is not the automation of quantity take-off, which is already well established in BIM-based workflows, nor the general idea of attaching circularity data to BIM elements, which the aforementioned works also pursue. The contribution is more specific: WASTEie2IFC is, to the best of the authors' knowledge, the first auditor-facing pipeline that writes CDW audit data into an IFC file against a publicly published, ISO 12006-3-compliant bSDD dictionary dedicated to construction and demolition waste. Where competing approaches place semantics in a custom graph, a proprietary database, or an ad-hoc Pset schema, WASTEie2IFC produces an IFC file whose property definitions are resolvable from a vendor-neutral source and whose classifications are grounded in the European List of Wastes. A downstream consumer, whether an LCA tool, a secondary-material marketplace, a compliance platform, or an IDS-based validator, can therefore interpret the enriched model without a bilateral agreement with the authoring tool. This standards-anchored interoperability, rather than automation per se, is the gap that the present paper addresses.

The introduced WASTEie2IFC web-based human-in-the-loop framework ([Šulc et al., 2026](#)) operationalizes this link between openBIM geometry and an open, standardized waste-data vocabulary. By providing a lightweight web interface, the framework lowers the technical and financial barrier to entry for auditors who may lack specialized BIM software licences or the high-performance hardware typically required for complex model management. The platform ingests

an IFC model, either authored in a BIM tool or produced by an automated scan-to-BIM pipeline, and separates deterministic computation from expert assessment: the algorithm parses the geometry and computes triangulated mesh volumes, while the auditor remains responsible for material diagnosis and EWC mapping through the web interface. The framework then generates a structured spreadsheet-based inventory for logistical use and an enriched IFC file in which WASTEie-compliant Psets and `IfcClassificationReference` links are attached directly to the relevant elements. This approach is validated on a historical railway station in Mladá Boleslav, Czech Republic, for which a high-fidelity digital model derived from terrestrial laser scanning is converted into a machine-readable inventory and an EU-Protocol-conformant audit record, and for which BIM-derived audit quantities are compared directly against the measured tonnages that left the site during the subsequent demolition works. The contribution of this work is twofold: (1) a digital framework that operationally bridges geometric BIM models with the publicly published bSDD WASTEie dictionary and EWC classifications, producing IFC files whose CDW semantics are resolvable against an ISO 12006-3-compliant, vendor-neutral data source; (2) a case-study evaluation in which the framework's audit estimates are quantitatively compared against the actual tonnages of construction and demolition waste produced during the subsequent deconstruction of the audited building, providing a direct validation that the pre-demolition-audit literature rarely affords.

2. Methodology

Figure 1 situates the WASTEie2IFC pipeline within the broader pre-demolition audit workflow: upstream scan-to-BIM tools deliver the geometric IFC model, the WASTEie2IFC web application enriches that model with standardized waste-classification data, and the resulting deliverables flow downstream into life-cycle assessment, secondary-material marketplaces, and EU-Protocol-conformant compliance reporting. The WASTEie2IFC pipeline takes a raw geometric IFC model of an existing building and returns a semantically enriched, machine-readable CDW deliverable comprising (i) an enriched IFC file with WASTEie-aligned Psets and EWC classifications attached to each physical element, and (ii) a spreadsheet report structured in accordance with the EU Protocol for pre-demolition audits ([European Commission, 2024](#)). The pipeline is organized as a

human-in-the-loop workflow in which deterministic computation, comprising geometry parsing, volume calculation, Pset writing, validation, and export, is cleanly separated from expert assessment, comprising material identification, hazard diagnosis, and EWC-code assignment. Figure 3 shows the system architecture; the remainder of this section walks through the five processing steps that this architecture executes, beginning with its inputs, outputs and assumptions.

Figure 1: Positioning of WASTEie2IFC within the pre-demolition audit workflow. Upstream scan-to-BIM pipelines deliver the geometric IFC model (left); the WASTEie2IFC web application enables the human-driven enrichment of that model with WASTEie-aligned Psets and EWC classifications (center); the resulting standardized deliverables flow downstream into life-cycle assessment tools, secondary-material marketplaces, and EU-Protocol-conformant compliance reporting (right).

WASTEie itself is a bSDD-published dictionary ([buildingSMART International, 2024b](#); [Teterov, 2024](#)) that extends IFC 4.3 with Psets describing the waste- and recycling-related attributes of construction materials and components. Because the dictionary is hosted on the bSDD platform, compatible tools resolve its Pset and property definitions at query time without any schema extension on the IFC side. WASTEie2IFC treats the dictionary as an authoritative external input rather

than as an internal artefact: the pipeline writes into Psets whose names, data types and allowed values are defined by WASTEie and whose definitions downstream consumers can retrieve directly from bSDD.

2.1. Inputs, outputs and assumptions

The pipeline consumes three inputs. The first is an IFC file conforming to schema IFC 4.3, containing physical `IfcElement` instances with populated `IfcProductDefinitionShape` body representations; the file may be authored directly in a BIM tool or produced by an automated scan-to-BIM pipeline such as Cloud2BIM (Nežerka and Zbirovský, 2025). The second is a pinned version of the WASTEie bSDD dictionary, providing the authoritative set of Psets, properties and allowed values. The third is the European List of Wastes, which provides the controlled vocabulary for CDW classification.

Two outputs are produced at the end of the pipeline: an enriched IFC file in which each processed element carries the WASTEie-defined Psets and an `IfcClassificationReference` linking it to its EWC code via `IfcRelAssociatesClassification`; and an Excel workbook structured in accordance with the EU Construction and Demolition Waste Management Protocol (European Commission, 2024), aggregating volumes by EWC fraction and by hazardous/non-hazardous flag.

Three working assumptions frame the pipeline. First, the input IFC model is assumed to represent as-built geometry with bounded, known uncertainty; the pipeline does not attempt geometric repair, and upstream scan-to-BIM fidelity dominates the end-to-end error budget (Section 3.1.2). Second, material identification is delegated to the human auditor; the algorithm does not perform automated material classification. Third, the bSDD dictionary is assumed to be reachable at session start and is cached locally for the duration of the session, so that transient API unavailability does not interrupt an in-progress audit.

2.2. System architecture

The WASTEie2IFC service is implemented in Python with a REST backend and a lightweight relational session store; neither the specific framework nor the persistence layer is methodologically load-bearing, and the architecture could be reproduced on any equivalent web stack without

Figure 2: Toggle-tree structure of WASTEie parameters selectable in the application.

affecting the enrichment logic described below. As shown in Figure 3, the system is organized in three architectural layers. An auditor-facing web interface handles IFC upload and the human-in-the-loop EWC mapping. The externally hosted bSDD service supplies the WASTEie dictionary as semantic input. The WASTEie2IFC backend itself contains two core modules: geometry-driven volume extraction built on `ifcopenshell` and Pset enrichment that writes the auditor’s mappings against the bSDD definitions. These modules jointly produce the two deliverables: the enriched IFC model and an EU-Protocol-conformant Excel report. Within this architecture, processing proceeds in five steps: (1) IFC ingestion and element enumeration, (2) geometry processing and volume computation, (3) interactive semantic enrichment by the auditor against the bSDD WASTEie dictionary (Figure 2), (4) validation of the enriched model, and (5) export to an enriched IFC file and to an EU-Protocol Excel report. Steps 1, 2, 4 and 5 are fully automated; step 3 is driven by the auditor through a 3D web interface.

Figure 3: System architecture of the WASTEie2IFC framework.

During processing, the application targets physical `IfcElement` entities (such as `IfcWall`, `IfcSlab`, and `IfcBeam`) and accurately calculates material volumes directly from the triangulated 3D geometry using the `ifcopenshell` library. Any elements with missing or malformed geometry are bypassed without halting the extraction. Finally, the application generates two primary outputs: a report structured in accordance with the EU Protocol for CDW audits, and an enriched IFC file in which the collected material data are written into a set of WASTEie-defined Psets attached to each processed element via `IfcRelDefinesByProperties`, including `Pset_MaterialRecycling`, `Pset_BuildingReuse`, `Pset_ComponentReuse`, and `Pset_Inspection`, together with an `IfcClassificationReference` linking the ele-

ment to its EWC code via `IfcRelAssociatesClassification`.

3. Case study

3.1. Railway station Mladá Boleslav

The reference case for this demonstration is the Mladá Boleslav railway station building in the Czech Republic. The building's structural system is characterized by load-bearing brick masonry and semi-battened wooden beam ceilings, which incorporate historical repairs, fine debris backfill, and reed-based suspended ceilings. Because the original as-built documentation was simplified and outdated, a high-fidelity point cloud was generated using terrestrial laser scanning. The initial raw point cloud of 504 million points was thinned to a minimum spacing of 0.01 m, resulting in a final dataset of 273 million points (a 46% reduction) that preserved essential geometric fidelity for modeling.

The IFC geometry was generated using the Cloud2BIM ([Zbirovský and Nežerka, 2025](#)) pipeline, which automatically converted floor-specific point clouds into parametric building elements, followed by refinement in BIM authoring tools to ensure structural coherence. The pre-demolition audit was performed by BIM specialists and engineers. In terms of workflow duration, conventional pre-demolition audits rely on manual on-site measurements and subjective expert assessment, which for complex buildings can take several days or even weeks. In contrast, the digital approach using the WASTEie2IFC application allowed for automated quantity take-offs directly from the high-fidelity BIM model in a matter of minutes, while the site visit and inspection could not be avoided.

3.1.1. Results and waste fraction analysis

To ensure precise volume calculations for secondary materials and reduce the margin of error inherent in purely visual estimations, the geometric data was supplemented with targeted physical interventions. For instance, the thickness of internal plaster on load-bearing brick masonry was verified through a series of on-site test probes, illustrated on the left of Figure 4, where the empirical measurement reduces volume calculation error margins relative to purely visual estimation. The audit determined an average thickness of 25 mm. This highly accurate quantitative data was

used in conjunction with wall surface areas extracted from the BIM model to calculate exact plaster volumes.

While a direct quantitative comparison to a traditional manual audit was not available for the Mladá Boleslav station, the framework reduces one important source of uncertainty relative to conventional visual estimation. Traditional pre-demolition audits often calculate volumes from simplified dimensional assumptions, which can fail to account for irregular geometries, historical cutouts, or structural degradation and may therefore bias volumetric estimates. WASTEie2IFC instead extracts triangulated mesh volumes from the `IfcElement` geometries via `ifcopenshell`. The resulting quantities remain bounded by the quality of the input BIM model, but they provide a reproducible baseline for secondary material quantification.

Figure 4: Physical probing during the pre-demolition audit. Execution of a test probe for estimating the average thickness of internal plaster, providing empirical data to minimise volume calculation error margins (left); historical fine-debris backfill and reed-based suspended ceilings identified during physical probing of the wooden beam ceiling constructions (right).

The findings were recorded within the `IfcWall` Psets through the WASTEie2IFC interface shown in Figure 5, which presents the toggle tab through which auditors enter standardized ma-

terial build-up data. Crucially, this included qualitative notes on local degradation, such as salt efflorescence and biological growth, which directly informs recycling suitability and prevents contaminated materials from entering clean secondary supply chains.

Figure 5: Toggle tab within the WASTEie2IFC interface for entering supplementary material information and standardized circularity data into an `IfcWall` entity.

Table 1 summarizes the automated waste quantities extracted from the digital 3D model. The framework successfully quantified large streams of highly recoverable materials, notably 1 841,07 m³ of masonry bricks suitable for recycled aggregate, and 128,31 m³ of timber.

Crucially, the framework facilitated the precise spatial mapping of 32.03 m³ of hazardous chimney structures (EWC 17 01 06*). The identification of this hazard was strictly diagnostic; human auditors conducted physical site surveys and chemical assessments to identify the presence of hazardous contaminants in the specific chimney masonry. Once identified on-site, the auditors utilized the WASTEie2IFC interface to select the corresponding `IfcWall` geometries and tag them with the hazardous EWC code. The framework then locked this semantic classification to the spatial coordinates of the chimney elements within the digital 3D model. This localization of hazardous materials is invaluable for demolition contractors, as it allows them to visually isolate the exact location of hazards, plan safe and selective dismantling sequences, and ensure that the primary

non-hazardous brick stream remains completely uncontaminated.

Table 1: Total estimated waste quantities by EWC category extracted via WASTEie2IFC for the Mladá Boleslav reference case.

EWC Code	Material category	Volume (m ³)	Waste type
17 01 02	Bricks (masonry walls and partitions)	1 841,07	Non-hazardous
17 01 06*	Bricks (contaminated chimney structure)	32.03	Hazardous
17 01 01	Concrete (plain, reinforced, aerated)	237.75	Non-hazardous
17 02 01	Timber and wood	128.31	Non-hazardous
17 01 03	Ceramics and tiles	14.29	Non-hazardous
17 04 07	Metals (steel, cast iron, aluminum)	12.83	Non-hazardous
17 02 02	Glass	0.16	Non-hazardous
17 09 04	Undefined / Other (mixed CDW)	14.57	Non-hazardous
Total estimated volume		2 281,01	

The extraction of these machine-readable metrics directly supports the reporting requirements of the EU Level(s) framework (specifically macro-objective 2) and the EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities. By calculating 1 841,07 m³ of masonry as a potentially clean fraction, the digital model furnishes the verifiable upper bound required to list these fractions on secondary material marketplaces prior to actual deconstruction; Section 3.1.2 examines how much of this potential was realized during the subsequent demolition. Furthermore, the spatial isolation of hazardous materials reduces the risk that contaminated chimney bricks are mixed with clean wall partitions and thereby downgrade recoverable masonry into a lower-value or hazardous stream. In this sense, the semantic enrichment provided by WASTEie2IFC supports higher-value recovery by linking quantity estimates, material diagnosis, and spatial location in a single audit deliverable.

3.1.2. *Ex-post validation against measured demolition tonnages*

A defining limitation of pre-demolition-audit research is that predicted quantities are rarely benchmarked against the tonnages that actually leave the site during subsequent deconstruction. For the Mladá Boleslav station, the demolition contractor’s waste consignment records became available after the demolition, enabling a direct ex-post comparison between the WASTEie2IFC predictions and the measured streams. To harmonize the two datasets, that is, volumes (m³) from the audit and masses (t) from the consignment records, the predicted volumes were converted to

tonnages using the bulk in-situ densities recommended by the EU CDW Protocol and the PA-RADE guidance (European Commission, 2024; Wahlström et al., 2019). The densities applied were 1.8 t/m³ for brick masonry, 2.3 t/m³ for plain concrete, 1.9 t/m³ for ceramics, 0.6 t/m³ for mixed wood/timber, 7.8 t/m³ for metals, 2.5 t/m³ for glass, and 1.6 t/m³ for mixed mineral CDW. Table 2 reports the resulting fraction-by-fraction comparison.

Table 2: Comparison of WASTEie2IFC audit estimates with measured demolition tonnages for the Mladá Boleslav railway station. Audit volumes were converted to tonnes using the literature bulk densities listed in the text; values are rounded.

EWC code	Fraction	Audit (m ³)	Audit (t)	Measured (t)	Δ (%)
17 01 02	Bricks, pure	1 841	3 372	1 849	+82
17 01 07	Mixed mineral rubble	n/a	n/a	3 103	n/a
17 01 01	Concrete	238	547	412	+33
17 01 03	Ceramics and tiles	14	27	(in 17 01 07)	n/a
<i>Sum of mineral fractions (02+07+01+03)</i>		n/a	3,946	5,363	-26
17 02 01	Wood	128	77	275	-72
17 04 07	Metals	13	100	n/a	n/a
17 02 02	Glass	0.2	0.4	n/a	n/a
17 01 06*	Hazardous chimney masonry	32	58	0 (isolated)	n/a
17 05 04	Soil and stones	n/a	n/a	2 593	n/a
17 03 02	Bituminous mixtures	n/a	n/a	108	n/a
17 06 04	Insulation	n/a	n/a	34	n/a
20 03 07	Bulky waste	n/a	n/a	45	n/a

Before interpreting the individual fractions, it is useful to situate the comparison at the aggregate level. The audit predicted approximately 4 146 t across all EWC categories it covered, whereas the measured consignment records total 8 418 t. The apparent gap of roughly 4 272 t, or 51% of the measured mass, is not a pipeline error and is almost fully explained by three distinct categories of material that the input IFC model did not represent. The first category is subsurface and external material, namely 2 593 t of soil and stones (EWC 17 05 04) and 108 t of bituminous mixtures (17 03 02) from foundations, excavations, and external paving, which a terrestrial laser scan of building interiors cannot observe. The second category is thin layered and non-structural material, namely 34 t of insulation (17 06 04), 45 t of bulky waste (20 03 07), and the additional non-structural wood/timber discussed below, which the scan-to-BIM process either did not resolve

at the level of a discrete `IfcElement` or did not classify as a load-bearing component and therefore omitted. The third category is a material-classification shift on site, in which a fraction of the brick masonry predicted by the audit as pure 17 01 02 was reclassified by the demolition contractor into the mixed-rubble code 17 01 07. The first two categories reflect genuine limitations of the upstream geometric capture; the third reflects an economic decision at the point of sorting, not an audit error (Gálvez-Martos et al., 2018). The remainder of this section therefore interprets the comparison by material, rather than by headline total, since an aggregated percentage conflates three structurally different sources of deviation.

For material streams represented in the BIM model, the deviations are interpretable rather than random. The predicted tonnage of brick masonry exceeds the measured tonnage recorded as pure brick (17 01 02), but the discrepancy is largely explained by the contractor reclassifying a substantial fraction of mineral rubble as mixed 17 01 07 rather than as pure 17 01 02. This is an economic decision taken on site, reflecting the marginal cost of additional sorting relative to the market value of the cleaner fraction, and not a direct calculation error in the audit. When the mineral fractions are summed across EWC codes 17 01 01, 17 01 02, 17 01 03 and 17 01 07, the aggregate audit estimate of approximately 3 946 t compares to a measured 5 363 t, a 26% underestimation at the total-mineral level.

The wood prediction, by contrast, is substantially lower than the measured tonnage (77 t predicted against 275 t measured, a 72% underestimation). This deviation is traceable to the upstream digital model rather than to the enrichment pipeline. The scan-to-BIM process captured the structural semi-battened timber beams but did not reconstruct non-structural elements such as floorboards, door and window frames, interior paneling, and roof carpentry, all of which contributed substantial mass to the actual waste stream. This finding substantiates the assertion made in Section 2.1, namely that end-to-end error in BIM-derived audits is dominated by the fidelity of the input geometric model rather than by the downstream calculation.

The operationally most important observation concerns hazardous material isolation. The audit identified 32 m³ of chimney masonry as hazardous (17 01 06*) and the demolition plan was sequenced accordingly. The consignment records contain no hazardous EWC entry, indicating

that the chimney material was successfully isolated on site and did not contaminate the primary 17 01 02 brick stream. Had the hazardous fraction been missed or incorrectly located, the entire mineral stream would have been liable to reclassification as hazardous, with a corresponding economic and environmental loss amounting, for this building alone, to a downgrade of several thousand tonnes from recoverable aggregate to controlled-landfill status.

Taken together, these results position WASTEie2IFC as a tool that produces reproducible audit estimates for the materials captured in the input IFC, surfaces incomplete geometric capture as the dominant source of deviation, and demonstrably supports the safe isolation of hazardous fractions. They also delineate the framework's current operational envelope: it is a reliable instrument for above-ground structural fabric, but it must be complemented by conventional site-investigation methods for subsurface and thin-layered fractions.

4. Discussion

The Mladá Boleslav case demonstrates that the principal digitalization challenge in pre-demolition auditing is not quantity extraction alone, but the conversion of quantities and expert diagnoses into interoperable data. WASTEie2IFC addresses this challenge by channeling audit outputs into an IFC structure that downstream stakeholders can consume without bilateral agreement. This standardized deliverable also enables workflows that are not practical with PDF reports or proprietary spreadsheets. Figure 6 illustrates one such extension by comparing a viewpoint in the openBIM model with the corresponding on-site location. Once the spatial registration between model and physical reality is resolved, the enriched model could be loaded into augmented- or extended-reality (XR) environments for on-site inspection, verification, and stakeholder review. Recent work on extended-reality applications for existing buildings demonstrates the maturity of this pipeline in adjacent domains such as heritage preservation and visualization (Duzenli et al., 2026). Its transfer to pre-demolition auditing would allow auditors to overlay EWC classifications on physical components, cross-check assignments in situ, and flag discrepancies through the BIM collaboration format for downstream resolution.

The ex-post comparison reported in Section 3.1.2 also clarifies where future accuracy gains should be sought. The 72% timber/wood underestimation observed at Mladá Boleslav originated

(a) Viewpoint within the openBIM model

(b) Corresponding location on-site

Figure 6: Alignment of the model and physical reality: comparison of the digital BIM model (a) with the corresponding on-site location (b), illustrating the spatial registration required for AR and XR applications.

in the digital model's omission of non-structural wood, and the absence of soil, bituminous, and insulation categories reflects a structural limitation of terrestrial laser scanning of building interiors (Valero et al., 2022; You et al., 2026b). These deviations indicate that the end-to-end reliability of BIM-derived audits is governed primarily by reality-capture coverage and modelling scope. Improvements should therefore focus on interior scanning of floor and roof cavities, external and subsurface surveys, and material-sensitive sensing for thin layered assemblies. The case also shows that a high-fidelity audit defines the recoverable clean fraction as a technical potential, while its realization depends on sorting effort, contractual incentives, and secondary-material markets. Targeted physical interventions, such as the 25 mm plaster thickness probes conducted in this study, remain essential because they calibrate the model where scan-to-BIM reconstruction is weakest and can be recorded directly in WASTEie Psets for downstream use (Bosché et al., 2015).

These operational advantages should be interpreted together with three limitations. First, the accuracy of the reported volumes is inherently limited by the geometric fidelity of the input IFC model: because the application extracts mesh volumes, any geometric deviation generated during scan-to-BIM reconstruction propagates directly into the reported CDW quantities. A wall reconstructed 50 mm thicker than its physical counterpart will therefore produce a proportionally inflated volume unless corrected by the auditor or upstream model validation. Second, while the bSDD WASTEie dictionary provides a comprehensive baseline for CDW classification, certain composite or highly specific material build-ups do not map cleanly onto a single standard EWC code; the present version of the framework resolves such cases by assigning the dominant fraction and recording the residual composition as a qualitative note in the Pset, but a more refined waste ontology would permit direct encoding of multi-fraction elements. Third, the present study reports a single case; although that case is unusually rich because measured demolition tonnages became available for comparison, generalization to other building typologies, in particular contemporary concrete-frame structures, industrial facilities, and timber-intensive residential buildings, remains to be established through further case work, and the balance between the three categories of deviation identified in Section 3.1.2 will almost certainly shift with the construction system under audit.

By generating enriched, standardized IFC models, WASTEie2IFC changes the status of the audit deliverable from a static report to reusable infrastructure for circular-economy decisions. The data can flow into LCA tools, help demolition contractors sequence logistics around hazardous material hotspots, and allow specific waste fractions to be listed on secondary-material marketplaces before physical deconstruction. The extracted metrics also support the reporting requirements of the EU Level(s) framework, specifically macro-objective 2 on resource-efficient and circular material life cycles, and of the EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities (Dodd et al., 2020; Díaz-López et al., 2021; Honic and De Wolf, 2023). The structure of the deliverable is furthermore compatible with the national audit procedures now being formalized at member state level, including Germany's DIN SPEC 91484:2023 (Deutsches Institut für Normung, 2023), France's statutory PEMD diagnosis (French Republic, 2020), and the Dutch BRL 2506 certification pathway for recycled aggregates (Stichting Bouwkwaliiteit, 2021). Because the semantic backbone is a publicly governed bSDD dictionary rather than a project-specific schema, data flowing through WASTEie2IFC can be re-validated by any stakeholder without access to the original authoring environment, a property that neither a custom graph representation nor a proprietary database offers without additional tooling.

5. Conclusion

This study addressed a practical barrier in circular construction: pre-demolition audits often produce static reports that cannot be reliably queried, validated, or ingested by downstream digital workflows. WASTEie2IFC was developed to close this gap by converting expert audit inputs into machine-readable IFC deliverables linked to the publicly available bSDD WASTEie dictionary and to European Waste Catalogue classifications.

The Mladá Boleslav case demonstrates that the framework can transform a scan-to-BIM model into a standardized material inventory and an enriched openBIM model suitable for pre-demolition decision making. The ex-post comparison with demolition consignment records showed that deviations were traceable mainly to the scope and fidelity of the input model, especially the omission of subsurface, thin-layered, and non-structural components, rather than to the semantic enrichment pipeline itself. For the material streams represented in the BIM model, the results provided

a reproducible basis for quantification, while the spatially explicit classification of contaminated (hazardous) chimney masonry supported its successful isolation during demolition.

The significance of this result is that the audit becomes more than a one-off compliance document. By binding geometry, quantities, EWC codes, and WASTEie-defined circularity properties inside an IFC file, the same deliverable can support demolition planning, LCA, secondary-material marketplaces, material passports, digital building logbooks, and automated checking against information requirements. The approach therefore shifts pre-demolition auditing from document-centric reporting toward interoperable data exchange.

The framework nevertheless remains bounded by the completeness of upstream reality capture and by the current granularity of waste ontologies for composite materials. Future work should therefore combine the enrichment workflow with improved capture protocols, IDS-based pre-export validation, clearer visual flagging of hazardous elements in the 3D viewer, and additional ex-post validation across building typologies. Standardized, machine-readable audits are not only a better reporting format; they are a prerequisite for making circular demolition decisions operational at scale.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Slávek Zbirovský: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Writing of original draft, Visualization. **Stanislav Šulc:** Methodology, Software, Validation, Writing of review and editing. **Vitalij Tetervov:** Conceptualization, writing and review. **Václav Nežerka:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing of review and editing.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used AI language model Claude 4.7 (Anthropic) in order to improve readability and language of the manuscript. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Data availability

The WASTEie2IFC web application is currently accessible at [<https://wasteie2ifc.fsv.cvut.cz>]. The bSDD WASTEie dictionary against which the framework writes its outputs is openly published and publicly accessible via the buildingSMART Data Dictionary at <https://search.bsdd.buildingsmart.org>.

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